

Donor Properties of 1-Amidino-O-Alkylureas Square Planar Cobalt(II) Complexes

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A series of yellow cobalt (II) complexes of 1-amidino-O-alkylureas (AAUH) are described. These form anhydrobases $[\text{Co}(\text{AAU})_2]$. These are non electrolytes and give magnetic moments in the range 2.3-2.5 B.M., indicating spin-paired square planar stereochemistry. In methanol, tetrahydrofuran and dioxan, the complexes undergo rapid oxidation, providing two electronic absorption bands, which are characteristic of all $3d^6$ cobalt (III) six co-ordinate complexes. However in acetone, the rate of oxidation is far slower and the spectra does not show the long wave length cobalt (III) band nor any band in the tetrahedral or octahedral cobalt (II) region but suggests the existence of a band beyond $1000 \text{ m}\mu$ region, which also points to a square planar disposition of the two ligands around cobalt (II).

In a number of articles, we have reported the results of the extensive investigations on the bis 1-amidino-O-alkylurea cobalt (III) complexes¹. All these studies were based on the oxidation of the light yellow cobalt(II) complexes of 1-amidino-O-alkylureas to one of cobalt(III). The present report concerns the syntheses, properties and finally the stereochemistry of the bis 1-amidino-O-alkylurea cobalt(II) complexes.

EXPERIMENTAL

1-amidino-O-methylurea, 1-amidino-O-ethylurea, 1-amidino-O-isopropylurea, 1-amidino-O-n-butylurea, 1-amidino-O-isobutylurea and 1-amidino-O-isoamylurea sulphates were prepared and purified according to published procedures². Methanol used was of E. Merck's G. R. variety.

A contraction similar to that described for the synthesis of black, nitrosylpentamine cobalt(II) chloride was used for our preparations³.

General method of preparation of bis 1-amidino-O-alkylurea cobalt(II) complexes: $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (1.2 g) and 1-amidino-O-alkylurea sulphate (1:2 ratio) were dissolved in water (15 ml) saturated with hydrogen. To this mixture hydrogen saturated liquor ammonia (5 ml) was added dropwise with vigorous stirring. A pale yellow precipitate separated which was filtered quickly through a sintered glass Buchner funnel in an atmosphere of hydrogen and washed with air free hydrogen saturated ice cold water until free from ammonia. This was then sucked well in an atmosphere of hydrogen and dried under vacuum over solid KOH and CaCl_2 .

General properties of bis 1-amidino-O-alkylurea cobalt(II) complexes: The complexes are insoluble in water, chloroform and benzene but soluble in alcohol, ether, tetrahydro-

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furan, dioxan, pyridine, β -picoline and acetonitrile giving a red solution due to oxidation to the cobaltic state. In moist condition they oxidise to a reddish product but in the solid dry state these are quite stable and can be preserved for months without any visible change. They do not decompose and oxidise even on heating upto 120° for hours. These are anhydrobases and liberate ammonia from ammonium salts followed by oxidation to cobalt (III) state. When boiled with water they oxidise to a red solution. The methyl derivative undergoes oxidation readily in comparison to the others. With the increase of the chain-length of the alkyl group resistance towards aerial oxidation increases. On treatment with acids they undergo decomposition.

TABLE I

Analyses and Colour of bis 1-amidino O-alkylurea Cobalt(II) Complexes

Compounds	Colour		Co %	N %
1. [Co (AMU) ₂]	Dirty yellow silky crystals	Found	20.6	38.8
		Calcd.	20.4	38.6
2. [Co (AEU) ₂]	Pale yellow	Found	18.8	35.0
		Calcd.	18.6	35.2
3. [Co (APIU) ₂]	Pale yellow	Found	17.1	32.6
		Calcd.	17.1	32.4
4. [Co (AB \equiv U) ₂]	Pale yellow	Found	15.6	30.2
		Calcd.	15.8	30.0
5. [Co (AB \cdot U) ₂]	Pale yellow	Found	15.7	30.3
		Calcd.	15.8	30.0
6. [Co (AA \cdot U) ₂]	Pale yellow	Found	14.8	28.0
		Calcd.	14.6	27.9

General Experimental procedure : Cobalt content was determined by decomposing the complex to cobalt oxides by ignition and then treating with concentrated HCl and HNO₃ and finally with concentrated H₂SO₄. Cobalt was finally weighed as anhydrous cobalt sulphate.

Nitrogen was estimated by semimicro Dumas combustion technique.

Electronic absorption spectra were recorded with the help of a Hilger Watts Uvispek Spectrophotometer using one cm. cells.

Conductance measurements in methanol were performed with a Philip's Conductivity bridge and a dip type cell.

Magnetic susceptibility measurements were taken in a Gouy Balance recently set up in our Laboratory. The sample was suspended from a single pan semimicro Mettler Analytical Balance into a magnetic field generated by a Polytronic Electromagnet, which was fed by 5 amp. current from A/C main via a Polytronic Rectifier cum current stabiliser. Recrystallised copper sulphate pentahydrate was used as the calibrant⁴ and a field of 8.85×10^3 gauss was used for measurements of the samples. Diamagnetic correction of the ligands was applied by the use of Pascal's constants⁵.

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RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The 1-amidino-O-alkylureas react with cobalt(II) salts in the presence of ammonia to precipitate bis 1-amidino-O-alkylurea cobalt(II). The complexes have been obtained in a pure form using a hydrogen atmosphere during syntheses and using air-free, hydrogen saturated water as the solvent medium. Whereas biguanide sulphate and cobalt(II) sulphate react under similar situations to precipitate bis-biguanide cobalt(II) sulphate or in the presence of sodium hydroxide, the bis-biguanide cobalt(II) hydroxide⁴, the 1-amidino-O-alkylureas provide under the same reaction conditions the cobalt(II) complexes as the anhydrobases. This behaviour is reminiscent of what has been observed in nickel(II) complexes of these ligands⁶. The contrast between these two series of closely related ligands may be traced to a weaker base strength of the 1-amidino-O-alkylureas⁷.

The complexes reported herein pertain to $3d^7$ cobalt(II) and possess a co-ordination number four. There has been a tremendous enthusiasm regarding the stereochemical assignments of cobalt(II) complexes from magnetic and spectral measurements. In a tetrahedral symmetry cobalt(II) will have a filled lower doublet and a half filled triplet. On the contrary, for a square planar case, due to a large separation in the energy of the $d_{x^2-y^2}$ and the d_{xy} orbital, electrons should be paired, so that only one unpaired electron will remain in the cobalt(II) orbitals. Considering the orbital contributions to the spin moment, a magnetic moment lying between 4.3 to 4.74 B.M. is regarded as associated with a tetrahedral structure. Values in the range 2.1 to 2.9 B.M. have been taken to indicate probable planar structure. For an octahedral spin paired case, the complexes have much lower orbital contribution and the magnetic moment usually lies in the range 1.7-2.0 B.M.^{8,9}. The measured magnetic moments of our complexes all lie within the range 2.2—2.5 B.M. Since the complexes are all anhydrobases, no other group being associated with the complex, we feel that the magnetic moments are truly indicative of a real square planar structure. In acetone solution, the complexes remain pale yellow and Beer's law is obeyed upto a concentration of 0.002 M in complex. This may be regarded as an evidence against any worthwhile degree of association thus lending further support to a co-ordination number four. Cobalt(II) bis-biguanide complexes also have afforded magnetic moment values lying within the range 2.3-2.6 B.M.⁴.

Tetrahedral cobalt(II) complexes generally have strong absorption bands within the 650 m μ -700 m μ region, whereas bands around 550 m μ are found in octahedral cobalt(II) complexes. It was observed that the crystal field bands in the spectra of tetrahedral cobalt(II) have molar extinction coefficients which are much larger than those found in either planar or octahedral complexes¹⁰⁻¹⁵. In a significant spectral study of planar, quadri-coordinate complexes of cobalt(II) with Schiff bases derived from salicylaldehyde, a sharp

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absorption band around $1200\text{ m}\mu$ has been claimed as diagnostic of square planar stereochemistry¹⁶. This study appears to have received confirmation¹⁷. We then searched a number of nonaqueous solvents, where the complex will not be oxidised so readily as to vitiate any dependable spectral measurements. We observed that in acetone and in low concentration, there is formed a fine yellow solution, which is reasonably stable to allow spectral measurements. The recorded spectra showed a peak around $335\text{ m}\mu$ and then it gradually faded out and after $900\text{ m}\mu$ showed signs of increasing. Since our spectrophotometer did not allow measurements beyond $1000\text{ m}\mu$, all that we observed was the suggestion of a peak beyond $1000\text{ m}\mu$, in conformity with the Japanese study¹⁶. Thus we feel that the partial spectral confirmation has been obtained for a planar structure. Besides the tetrahedral region and the octahedral region showed no sign of a band ruling out such stereochemistry. Reflectance spectra around this $1200\text{ m}\mu$ region could have given unequivocal spectral proof about stereochemical pattern. Unfortunately we were not equipped to do this.

The complex, however, was more susceptible to solvents, which are known as better donors. Thus in methanol, tetrahydrofuran and also in dioxan, there was much quicker oxidation and the usual two cobalt(III) six co-ordinate absorption bands around $330\text{-}350\text{ m}\mu$ and around $480\text{-}500\text{ m}\mu$ were found to be there^{18,19}.

FIG 1. Electronic absorption spectra of
 (A) $[\text{Co}(\text{AEU})_2]$, 0.0005M ; solvent, acetone.
 (B) $[\text{Co}(\text{AEU})_2]$, 0.001M ; solvent, acetone; after 24 hours.
 (C) $[\text{Co}(\text{AEU})_2]$, 0.001M ; solvent, methanol; after 15 minutes.
 (D) $[\text{Co}(\text{AEU})_2]$, 0.001M ; solvent, methanol; after 24 hours.

The oxidation was generally complete over 24 hr. and differed from the spectra of the hydroxoquo bis 1-amidiono-O-alkylurea cobalt(III) spectra¹⁶. Further measurements of

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conductance in methanol indicated the non-electrolytic nature of the complexes in general or a very strong ion-pair effect. Whereas the conductance values for uni-univalent electrolyte are 90-110 mhos, we observed values around 20 mhos. Besides during the entire course of oxidation, there was no significant change in the conductance values. These point to the fact that oxidised product, too is a non electrolyte. However, we have no definite experimental evidence to commit about the exact composition or nature of this species.

TABLE II
Magnetic susceptibility measurements

Temp.=306°K.

Compounds	Dia. corr. $\times 10^6$	χ_M (Corr.) $\times 10^6$	$\mu_{eff.}$ (B.M.)*
1. [Co (AMU) ₂]	98.0	2221	2.34
2. [Co (AEU) ₂]	121.7	2299	2.36
3. [Co (APIU) ₂]	145.4	2595	2.52
4. [Co (ABIU) ₂]	169.2	2300	2.36
5. [Co (AB ⁿ U) ₂]	169.2	2201	2.32
6. [Co (AAiU) ₂]	190.8	2600	2.52

*Calculated from χ_M (Corr.) using the Curie equation $\mu_{eff.} = 2.84 \chi_M$ (corr.) $\times T^{\frac{1}{2}}$
 AMUH= 1-amidino-O-methylurea; AEUH= 1-amidino-O-ethylurea;
 APⁱUH= 1-amidino-O-isopropylurea; ABⁿUH= 1-amidino-O-butylurea;
 ABⁱUH= 1-amidino-O-isobutylurea; AAⁱUH= 1-amidino-O-isoamylurea.

TABLE III
Conductance measurements in methanol at 32°.

Compounds	Molar conductance Λ_M mhos cm^2 mole ⁻¹	
	After 15 minutes	After 24 hours.
1. [Co (AMU) ₂]	21	23
2. [Co (AEU) ₂]	11	18
3. [Co (AP ⁱ U) ₂]	21	23
4. [Co (AB ⁱ U) ₂]	20	21
5. [Co (AB ⁿ U) ₂]	21	22
6. [Co (AA ⁱ U) ₂]	20	23

Thus we tentatively assign the following square planar structure to the cobalt(II) complexes.

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